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HYPOTHYROIDISM AND AGING: SEARCH FOR PROTECTIVE FACTORS

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Annotation. Finding key links in the aging process is one of the main tasks in the development of geriatrics. More and more research in recent years has been devoted to the study of geroprotective mechanisms and the influence of various conditions and diseases on aging in general. Of particular importance are the determination of age-related involutive processes in the human body, deciding whether they are part of normal aging or a pathology that needs to be corrected in old age. An important age-associated process is a change in the activity of the endocrine system, one example of which is disturbances in the functioning of the thyroid gland. The high prevalence of hypothyroidism in old age explains the relevance of this topic and our interest in studying it. Our goal was to evaluate the impact of decreased thyroid function on the course of diseases in elderly patients. We conducted a review of the literature over the past 10 years on the treatment of hypothyroidism in geriatric patients, and identified the most pressing problems associated with compensation for this pathology in elderly patients. Data on the relationship between hypothyroidism and major geriatric syndromes were studied, with special attention paid to the relationship with cognitive impairment and emotional disturbances.

Keywords: hypothyroidism; subclinical hypothyroidism; longevity; aging; hormone therapy; thyroid-stimulating hormone.

ГИПОТИРЕОЗ И СТАРЕНИЕ: ПОИСК ЗАЩИТНЫХ ФАКТОРОВ

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Аннотация. Поиск ключевых звеньев процесса старения является одной из основных задач развития гериатрии. Все больше исследований в последние годы посвящено изучению геропротекторных механизмов и влияния

различных состояний и заболеваний на старение в целом. Особое значение имеют определение возрастных инволютивных процессов в организме человека, решение вопроса о том, являются ли они частью нормального старения или патологией, требующей коррекции в старости. Важным возрастным процессом является изменение деятельности эндокринной системы, примером которого являются нарушения функционирования щитовидной железы. Высокая распространенность гипотиреоза в пожилом возрасте объясняет актуальность этой темы и наш интерес к ее изучению. Нашей целью было оценить влияние снижения функции щитовидной железы на течение заболеваний у пациентов пожилого возраста. Мы провели обзор литературы за последние 10 лет по лечению гипотиреоза у гериатрических больных и выявили наиболее актуальные проблемы, связанные с компенсацией этой патологии у пожилых пациентов. Изучены данные о связи гипотиреоза с основными гериатрическими синдромами, при этом особое внимание уделено связи с когнитивными нарушениями и эмоциональными нарушениями.

Ключевые слова: гипотиреоз; субклинический гипотиреоз; долголетие; старение; гормональная терапия; тиреотропный гормон.

Introduction. One of the main directions in the development of geriatrics is the search for protective mechanisms in aging in order to increase the duration and improve the quality of life, which depend not only on the level and availability of medicine, but also on the completeness of understanding of these mechanisms, on the ability to apply knowledge in practice. Although aging is a natural process for the body, the goal of many scientific studies in recent years is not only to understand the aging process, but also to find key points of influence for the purpose of geroprotection. Thyroid hormones (TG) regulate the rate of metabolic processes in the body, change the activity of the adrenergic system, affect peripheral vascular resistance, enhance glycogenolysis and glycogenesis with specific contrainsular activity [1, 2]. During the aging process, the dynamics of many processes in the thyroid gland change: the thyroid gland's absorption of radioactive iodine and thyroxine secretion decrease, the metabolism and clearance of thyroxine slow down, as well as the peripheral conversion of thyroxine to triiodothyronine [1, 2]. The most common thyroid pathology in old age is hypothyroidism, characterized by persistent deficiency of thyroid hormones, namely its subclinical form [1]. Understanding the pathogenesis of these changes

helps to compensate for hypothyroidism in geriatric patients with maximum efficiency and safety.

Thyrostropic hormone is one of the main markers of hypothyrosis.

Many symptoms of hypothyroidism in old age are not clearly expressed, some of them (fatigue, muscle weakness, dry skin, tendency to constipation) are regarded as signs of “normal aging” [3]. Thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) is the main marker for diagnosing hypothyroidism; reference intervals for this hormone are important in determining treatment tactics. When discussing optimal TSH levels in old age, one should refer to studies to determine their reference values. The NHANES III study conducted in the USA and the SHIP study of a healthy population in Germany are similar in their goals - to determine reference values among a healthy population [4, 5]. The NHANES III study took place from 1988 to 1994. for the purpose of developing and formulating national health standards. The total sample did not include persons under 12 years of age with goiter, those receiving medications that affect the thyroid gland, and pregnant women. In addition, patients taking sex hormones, lithium, as well as those who had elevated antibodies to the thyroid gland were excluded. In the group of participants, 97.5% had an upper limit of TSH of 3.5 mU/L [5, 6]. The SHIP study included a control group of 1488 people without ultrasound signs of thyroid enlargement, changes in thyroid echogenicity and nodules. The study participants underwent a series of laboratory tests to form reference indicators for a healthy population. When analyzing the data obtained in the study, the upper limit for TSH was 2.2 mU/L [5, 6]. Despite the results of large cohort studies, the upper limit of TSH has not been adjusted according to these values. After a detailed assessment of the results obtained and their discussion in the USA, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) determined the upper limit of TSH as 4.0 mU/l. Arguments in favor of this decision: a) lack of evidence that prescribing thyroxine therapy to patients with a TSH level of 2.5–4.0 mU/l (and even 4.0–10.0 mU/l) has any benefits from the perspective of long-term prognosis, especially in terms of reducing mortality from cardiovascular pathology; b) classifying 5% of the population who do not have any diseases as patients with hypothyroidism will lead to enormous financial costs, as well as emotional and personal disorders in this category [1, 3]. In studies aimed at studying the prevalence of subclinical and manifest hypothyroidism in the elderly, the average age of the study group rarely exceeded 70 years, and there are very few studies with a sample of centenarians. At the Russian Gerontological Research and Clinical Center, as part of the federal

program “Healthy Longevity,” a comprehensive medical geriatric examination of citizens over 90 years of age was carried out.

The purpose of the study. It was necessary to assess the functional, cognitive and emotional status of centenarians to determine the amount of necessary assistance from social services and medical personnel; in addition, an analysis of thyroid function was carried out according to laboratory examination data [7]. According to the register of super centenarians of Samarkand, 82 people aged from 95 to 105 years were recruited, the median TSH was 2.26 (1.8–3.6) mU/l (data from 64 centenarians were analyzed). In most of the study participants, TSH was within the reference values (50 people, 78.1%), an increase in TSH level was detected in 12 centenarians (18.8%), in 2 (3.1%) there was a decrease in TSH level to 0.07 mU/l.

Result. may indicate the need for further study of larger cohorts of centenarians in order to determine an individual approach to therapy for this age group.

Influence of hypothyroidism on lipid metabolism. In old age, lipid metabolism plays an important role in achieving compensation for many diseases, especially cardiovascular diseases. In subclinical hypothyroidism, there is an increase in the level of lipoprotein(a), containing the apolipoprotein-A molecule connected to apolipoprotein-B-100, a component of very low-density lipoproteins, which gives lipoprotein(a) atherogenic and thrombogenic properties [8]. In a study by V. Asvold et al. In 30,656 people without thyroid disease, the effect of hypothyroidism on lipid metabolism was studied. When analyzing the results, it was found that impaired lipid metabolism in subclinical hypothyroidism is expressed in increased levels of total cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, as well as an increase in the ratio of LDL/high-density lipoprotein (HDL) and triglycerides (TG)/HDL. It has also been found that early initiation of replacement therapy and achievement of a euthyroid state significantly improves the LDL/HDL ratio, which reduces the risk of cardiovascular disease [9]. In a study by M. Pandrc et al. An analysis was conducted of the effectiveness of replacement therapy for subclinical hypothyroidism (defined as a TSH level of 4–10 mU/l with a normal free thyroxine (T4f) value in 35 patients, whose average age was 51.6 ± 15.4 years). When assessing the results of a biochemical study after a course of replacement therapy, a decrease was noted in such indicators as the level of homocysteine ($p = 0.03$), glycated hemoglobin ($p = 0.001$), total cholesterol ($p = 0.001$), triglycerides ($p = 0.007$), lipoproteins (a) ($p < 0.001$) [10]. Thus, in patients with

subclinical hypothyroidism, it is necessary to identify non-target values of lipid metabolism and adjust them in accordance with individual cardiovascular risks.

Influence of hypothyrosis on carbohydrate metabolism. Disorders of carbohydrate metabolism are one of the most common pathologies in the elderly. We analyzed studies assessing the impact of decreased thyroid function on the condition of patients with metabolic disorders. In a prospective population-based cohort study, L. Chaker et al. TSH and fT4 indicators were analyzed among participants over the age of 65 years. When analyzing the data, it was found that higher TSH levels and lower fT4 levels are associated with a higher risk of developing type 2 diabetes and progression from prediabetes to diabetes. Both overt and subclinical hypothyroidism were associated with decreased tissue sensitivity to insulin and decreased glucose tolerance. This may be important in achieving compensation for various disorders of carbohydrate metabolism [11]. Thus, in patients with various disorders of carbohydrate metabolism, it is important to evaluate thyroid function. Achieving a euthyroid state in this group may improve the prognosis of diseases.

Hypothyroidosis and cardiovascular diseases. One of the diseases that requires special care in correction in patients with hypothyroidism is coronary heart disease (CHD). There is an opinion that hypothyroidism due to atherogenic effects contributes to the development and progression of coronary artery disease [2]. In a study by N. Rodondi et al. The risk of developing coronary heart disease was assessed in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism. The evaluation included data from 25,977 patients based on the MEDLINE and EMBASE databases (1950 to May 31, 2010). When assessing the results, data were obtained demonstrating that subclinical hypothyroidism was associated with an increased risk of developing coronary artery disease, especially in patients with a TSH concentration of 10 mU/L or higher [12]. In patients with coronary artery disease, it is necessary to assess the hormonal status and individually determine approaches to compensation for thyroid diseases.

Hypothyrosis and osteoporosis. In old age, diseases of the musculoskeletal system are much more common than in young people. A decrease in the level of thyroid hormones can disrupt bone turnover by reducing the activity of osteoblasts. At the moment, there is no consensus on the need to compensate for hypothyroidism in order to prevent bone diseases [13]. Osteoporosis is the most common metabolic bone disease and is characterized by a decrease in bone mineral density, leading to an increased risk of fractures. In bone tissue,

triiodothyronine (T3) receptors interact with the alpha isoform of the nuclear thyroid hormone receptor in osteoblasts, T3 stimulates osteoblast activity (differentiation and proliferation, as well as bone matrix synthesis and mineralization). However, to date, studies have not been able to identify a reliable connection between the occurrence of hypothyroidism and the incidence of osteoporosis; the connection between a decrease in the level of thyroid hormones and an increased risk of fractures has also not been established [14]. Further research is needed to determine the need for correction of hypothyroidism in patients with osteoporosis.

Hypothyroidosis and geriatric syndromes. The functional state of the thyroid gland can influence the prevalence of geriatric syndromes, that is, age-associated clinical conditions that worsen quality of life and increase the risk of adverse outcomes. Patients with reduced thyroid function in old age are more likely to exhibit decreased cognitive function, anxiety and depressive symptoms, and a higher incidence of malnutrition and sarcopenia [15]. Cognitive impairments in old age are much more common than in young people [2, 15]. One of the reasons for the decline in cognitive functions in geriatric patients may be a dysfunction of the thyroid gland. Thus, in a study by S. Recker et al. The levels of anxiety, depression, and self-assessment of quality of life were assessed after levothyroxine replacement therapy for subclinical hypothyroidism in a group of young and elderly patients. The researchers assessed the dynamics of quality of life indicators using the SF-36 and ThyPRO questionnaires, and cognitive functions after 6 months of therapy. When analyzing the data, it was found that in the group of elderly patients there was a significant improvement in cognitive functions, improved quality of life, and decreased rates of anxiety and depression [16].

Therapy of hypothyroidia in elderly patients. The prescription of hormone replacement therapy in old age in patients with hypothyroidism has its own characteristics in comparison with the general population. Titration of the dose of levothyroxine requires more time and smaller increments of increasing the dose of drugs. When calculating the dose of levothyroxine in patients with severe concomitant pathologies, one should start with minimal doses (6.25–12.5 mcg), increasing the dose by 25 mcg every 2 months until TSH levels are normalized [1, 3, 4]. This careful dose titration allows older patients to better tolerate therapy. There is an opinion that if it is difficult to compensate for hypothyroidism in elderly patients, the TSH indicator can be within the limits not exceeding the values characteristic of subclinical hypothyroidism (not higher than

10 mU/l), and the period for selecting the optimal dose can reach 6 months [19, 20].

Conclusion. There is still no consensus on what role a decrease in thyroid function plays in the aging process, but subclinical hypothyroidism cannot be considered a natural process in old age. Correction of this pathology in elderly patients requires an individual approach; the goals of therapy should be selected by a specialist depending on concomitant diseases, the presence of cardiovascular and metabolic diseases, and the degree of their compensation. It is necessary to develop algorithms for compensation of hypothyroidism in old age, including in different age subgroups of patients over 60 years of age. To solve this problem, further research into the effectiveness and safety of therapy for subclinical hypothyroidism is required.

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